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Introduction-

Irritable Bowel Syndrome (IBS) is a common functional chronic gastrointestinal disorder that can cause various digestive symptoms such as abdominal pain, change in frequency and form of stool and other common symptoms. There is hardly any pathological changes structurally of gastrointestinal tract. At time when a person has irritable bowel syndrome (IBS), whether it's marked by frequent bouts of diarrhoea (IBS-D), constipation (IBS-C), mixed symptoms (IBS-M), and unclassified (IBS-U). diarrhoea is the prevalent symptom of IBS-D. Constipation is the prevalent symptom of IBS-C. IBS determination depends on clinical side effects and the rejection of substantial illnesses.[1-3]

It shows the prevalence of IBS in the Indian community varies from 0.4% to 4.2% [4,5,6,7].

IBS common symptoms include:

- Abdominal pain
- Frequently feeling cramping and bloating
- Bowel movements which frequently alternate between diarrhea and constipation
- changes in how often one experiences a bowel movement (often skipping days or going multiple times in a day).

This is not normal.

Digestion should be smooth and easy, barely being noticed by the person without any pain or excessive gas. Bowel movements should be 1-3x daily, and be smooth and easy to pass without being so soft it is

messy and difficult to clean oneself. A normal stool should have the appearance of a "brown sausage or snake".

Diagnosis is made based on the following criteria:

The patient has had recurrent abdominal pain/discomfort at least 3 days per month during the past 3 months, and experienced at least two of the below:

- Symptoms improve with defecation
- Onset is associated with a change in stool frequency
- Onset is associated with a change in stool form or appearance
- Mucorrhea (mucous with bowel movements)
- Abdominal bloating and gas

The reason for the very low prevalence of IBS in the recent global study might be related to the design of the study. IBS Symptom range from mild to severe to extent where quality of life is compromised. IBS has significant impact on health care cost along with effect on economy of nation.

The prime concern is to try anything to relieve your symptoms.

Case Presentation-

A Female patient aged 32 years diagnosed as a case of Irritable Bowel Syndrome with diarrhoea presented as Indigestion, loose motion, Mucorrea (will indicates the loss of high amounts of mucus along the faeces), foamy poop, motion with pain, tenesmus, Abdominal distention and itching of anal region since 2019. In year 2019 colonoscopy and endoscopy done. She is diagnosed with gluten allergy. Stool was acidic in nature. In year 2019 this started after abortion at the gestational period of 5 and half month. She is feeling overall fatigue due to this the quality of life was compromised and did not able to concentrate on work. Her weight measured 54 kgs, height is 166 cm, blood pressure recorded was mm hg. Her haemoglobin levels were.....

Treatment Protocol:

Naturopathy treatments

Fasting- 3 days of starting with lemon water and fruit juice

Water enema - Continuous for 4 days in the starting of treatment followed by twice in a week.

Hot/ Cold Hip Bath (Alternate Hip Bath)- Hot and cold in 3:1 minutes ratio 3 times in one sitting. A brisk walk for 30 minutes is recommended following the hip bath.

Gastro hepatic Pack – 10 minutes, 21 days

Cold Abdomen pack - 20 minutes daily

Sun Bath - 3 days in a week for 25-30 minutes.

Massage to Abdomen– 20 minutes, 12 days

Cold Hip Bath – 20 minutes, 12 days

Mud pack to abdomen -20 minutes daily (12 days)

Full body Mud Bath – 60 minutes once a week

Acupuncture- ST25,28,36,37, CV4, CV6, SP15,6 BL25,20,23,33,34,57, TE6, LI4,11,

Massage- 30 minute of abdominal Massage for 3 weeks.

Yoga Therapy -21 days:

Yogasana:- 1 hour daily

Sukshma vyayams, Tadasana, Tiryak tadasana, Tatichakrasana, Trikonasana, Ardhchakrasana, Padhastasana, Vakrasana, Pavanmuktasana, Uttanpadasana, Ardhhalasana, Bhujangasana, Tiryakbhujangasana, Shalabhasana,

PRANAYAMA:-

Bhastrika, Nadishodhan, Bhramri

KRIYAS:-

Kapalbhati, Agnisara.

BANDHA:- Uddiyan bandha.

MEDITATION- Aum chanting and Yog nidra,

Diet Therapy:-

Diet chart-

Early morning: Luke Warm water

Mid-morning: 1 Warm water+ 1lemon +1 Teaspoonful honey

Breakfast: vegetable/ fruit/ fruits juice/ coconut water

Lunch: chapatti + moong dal +rice(unpolished)+boild vegetable+soup+salad

Evening: homemade soup/butter milk/fruits

Dinner: oats/ moongdal kichadi/chapati+ boiled vegetable

Note: cereals must be wheat, rice, oats, finger millet, foxtail millet, buckwheat with ratio of wheat flour (50% +ragi flour (30%) +20 %(any millet)

Avoid- refind (flour, sugar,salt), oily/spicy/packed/fast/Animal food, Beans, Taro root, pea, black gram beans, dairy products.

According to a 2022 review, intestinal bacteria in human gut communicate with both your brain and your digestive system. When the signals between bacteria, brain, and gut fall out of balance, your emotions, sensations, and digestive functions can all be affected. Yoga Nidra is one of the best solutions to deal with digestive issues. It is performed while lying still on the ground. It has a profoundly calming effect that calms a stressed-out nervous system, tense muscles, and a busy mind.

Results-

<u>S.No.</u>	<u>Name of the parameter</u>	<u>Before naturopathy & Yoga practice</u>	<u>After naturopathy & Yoga practice</u>
1	Pain Abdomen	10	2
2	Quality of life	10	2
3	Hemoglobin level
4	Frequency of motion	8-10	1-2

Advice given to the patient:

Periodic fasting to restore gut health.

Sunbath daily for 15-20 minutes.

Yog/ Pranayam daily for minimum 45 min.

Cold Abdomen Pack

Discussion and conclusion-

The study results strongly support that yoga & Naturopathy could potentially play a beneficial role in management of Irritable Bowel Syndrome, a condition of disturbed gut health. The holistic approach of yoga & Naturopathy is rooted in natural healing methods and help alleviate symptoms, enhance gut health and wellbeing. The stretching and strengthening acts of Yoga significantly increase abdominal muscle flexibility and releases the stress of muscles, thereby relieving the symptoms arising out of IBS. Observing fast for certain time period under the guidance of a Naturopath helps to restore the bacterial flora and gut health. This combined with dietary modification, meditation and relaxation help to maintain gut flora and gut-brain axis. Furthermore, the manipulative therapy augments increased blood circulation to the abdominal area and organs related to digestive system ensuring nourishment and healing digestive track. The combination therapy of specific aasanas, breathing exercises, naturopathy interventions and relaxation techniques have proved beneficial in reducing both intensity and frequency of symptoms of the study subjects. Naturopathy relies on holistic healing which rests on twin elements of lifestyle modification and nutritive focus. The study strongly asserts to boost nutrition by including probiotic rich foods and excluding processed foods. Additionally, it strongly supports lifestyle modifications, specifically the improved eating patterns, fasting at regular intervals, intermittent breaks to relax mind and body.

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